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MECHANISMS OF INCREASING LISTENING SKILLS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to methods of formation of students' listening ability. Linguistic forecasting is facilitated by the skill of combining words. Knowing the rules of combinability of lexical units, students are more and less likely to be able to predict the content of incoming information, since the combinability of words in the language is limited.

Key words: *listening, communication situation, vocabulary, interpretation, information, characteristics, memory.*

Listening, as any process, is based on certain psychophysiological mechanisms: perception, recognition and understanding.

The mechanisms of perception include the mechanism of internal pronunciation, operational and long-term memory, identification (comparison), anticipation (probabilistic forecasting).

The success of listening is related to the mechanisms of the so-called auditory memory and depends on the size of the “operational unit of perception,” i.e., the ability to retain segments of speech in memory. The process of understanding an audio text and the possibility of its subsequent interpretation depend on the ability to retain perceived segments of speech in memory. However, auditory reception of information is impossible without the participation of internal pronunciation. The effect of

understanding depends on the success of the “internal imitation” of audible speech. Thanks to the mechanism of internal pronunciation, sound images turn into articulatory ones, and an “internal imitation” of the perceived audio fragment occurs. If we imitate correctly, then we perceive correctly.

When perceiving speech, there is a constant identification of incoming signals and patterns that are stored in our memory. At the same time, the identification process is connected with a person’s past experience, as well as with his sensory-emotional sphere. Obviously, the better developed long-term memory, the more effective identification occurs.

Researchers have found that even before the start of perception, as soon as the listening attitude appears, the articulatory organs already show minimal activity. Due to this, certain patterns are aroused in the listener's cognition. Such pre-tuning is the basis for the action of the anticipation or forecasting mechanism, which makes it possible to predict their end from the beginning of a word or phrase. There are linguistic and semantic forecasting.

Imagine hearing the beginning of the phrase “As war ein schöner, sonniger...”. Having some language experience, it is not difficult for you to guess what word this phrase will end with.

Semantic forecasting is provided by the context, the communication situation, the personal experience of the listener, and his knowledge. The success of semantic prediction largely depends on the expectations of the listener.

The richer our knowledge about the world, a specific topic or situation, the richer our vocabulary, the greater our ability to predict content and use context clues.

But recognition is not yet understanding. The basis of understanding is the mechanism of comprehension, which operates already at the level of actual awareness on the basis of the analytical and synthetic activity of the brain. The comprehension mechanism compresses phrases and individual text fragments by omitting details and, leaving only semantic milestones in memory, frees it up to receive a new piece of information.

The main characteristics of understanding are completeness, accuracy, depth.

The depth of penetration into the meaning of the perceived information indicates the level of understanding. As a rule, there are two main levels of understanding: the meaning of language units, the level of facts and meaning (critical).

But there is no single concept on this matter. Thus, A. R. Luria and other researchers identify the following levels of understanding the text:

- fragmented (individual LE);
- global (message topics);
- detailed (facts);
- critical (subtext).

Levels of understanding allow us to judge student learning levels and specify learning goals.

So, the size of the operational unit of perception (auditory working memory) depends on internal imitation (correct imitate → correctly recognize) as a result → identification (continuous comparison of perceived speech with samples of long-term memory), i.e the better the long-term memory, the better the identification.

The success of listening depends on a preliminary attitude towards the text being listened to. In essence, this is the basis for the action of the anticipation mechanism, a kind of anticipatory reflection of reality. The listener moves from recognition to comprehension.

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